

Measuring volumetric urban design: Compression, multi-level connectedness, and functional mix in transit-oriented developments in Hong Kong

Dongsheng He^{*1,2}, Guibo Sun^{†3}

¹School of Geography, University of Leeds, Leeds, UK

²Healthy and Sustainable Places Data Service, University of Leeds, Leeds, UK

³Department of Planning, Property and Environmental Management, The University of Manchester, UK

GISRUK 2026

Summary

Conventional urban form metrics, largely two-dimensional, are ill-equipped to capture these volumetric characteristics. This study addresses this limitation by developing quantitative metrics for three core elements of volumetric urban design: compression, multi-level connectedness, and functional mix. Drawing on high-resolution data on pedestrian networks, building data, and points of interest, we analyse case metro station areas in Hong Kong. The results show that 57% of buildings exhibit mixed use, characterised by pronounced functional stratification: employment- and visitor-oriented activities are concentrated within podiums, while residential uses dominate the upper floors. In contrast, conventional two-dimensional measures fail to capture up to 91% of spatial compression and 52% of pedestrian connectedness, and systematically misclassify all buildings as mono-functional. By explicitly accounting for multi-level connectivity, intensified space use, and vertical functional mix—key hallmarks of volumetric cities—our approach proposes a transferable framework for measuring and analysing volumetric urban design.

KEYWORDS: Volumetric city, urban design, transit-oriented development, pedestrian networks, High-density cities

1. Introduction to guidelines

Cities worldwide face the persistent challenge of balancing rapid population growth with limited available land, a dilemma that is especially acute in Asia (Al-Kodmany, 2018; Wang, 2020). In response, urban development has increasingly focused on creating high-density, highly connected, and multifunctional environments to maximise land use efficiency (Harris, 2015). Recently, the concept of the volumetric city has emerged, capturing the complexity and multi-layered nature of built environments in Asian cities (Bruyns et al., 2021; Shelton et al., 2013). The volumetric urban design extends beyond mere verticality, encompassing the compression and integration of public spaces and buildings to accommodate diverse urban functions within interior and multi-level spatial configurations.

Volumetric urban design builds on earlier urban theories, such as new urbanism, the compact city, and vertical urbanism (Lin & Gámez, 2018), all of which advocate dense, mixed-use, and walkable environments in response to car-oriented development and urban sprawl. These ideas have shaped contemporary planning movements, including the 15-minute city. Specifically, vertical urbanism extends these principles to high-rise, space-efficient environments, shifting from the modernist focus on skyscrapers toward more integrated, socially engaging three-dimensional systems that connect infrastructure, buildings, and public spaces across vertical and horizontal layers (Harris, 2015). While verticality has characterised large-scale developments in cities such as New York, Dubai, and Chicago, recent research highlights the volumetric city as a special model, particularly evident in Asian contexts (McNeill, 2020). In Hong Kong, a volumetric development is characterised by highly compressed, multi-layered, and internalised environments that integrate buildings, pedestrian networks, and

* D.He@leeds.ac.uk

† Guibo.sun@manchester.ac.uk

privately owned public spaces (Shelton et al., 2013). Volumetric design is thus best understood through key elements such as density, compactness, diversity, and connectedness (Lehmann, 2016), which capture both the physical compression of space and the integration of diverse functions across multiple levels (Bruyns et al., 2021). Despite increasing attention, most current studies rely on narrative and qualitative approaches to understand these complex, multi-layered urban forms (Lehmann, 2016).

Using Hong Kong as the case city, this paper aims to measure the volumetric urban design, with a focus on compression, connectedness, and functional mix. The first defining feature of volumetric design is the integration of three-dimensional pedestrian networks that connect multiple layers both vertically and horizontally (Sun et al., 2021). Public sectors and private developers provide extensive elevated pedestrian systems with public access, increasing street connectivity, reducing detours, and facilitating smooth pedestrian movement among buildings (Tan & QL Xue, 2014). This principle also underpins the urban design approach that creates highly connected, multi-layered, and internalised environments through the seamless integration of buildings, open spaces, and streets (Villani et al., 2022). Despite growing recognition of these multi-layered characteristics in high-density cities (Harris, 2015), most studies still rely on a figure-ground approach, focusing on mono-functional land plots, street centroid lines, or building footprints. Recent work has introduced new methods to capture the vertical complexity, such as function composition using cadastral data (Dovey & Pafka, 2017), multi-scale density (Pafka, 2023), and compression via building volumes (Wang et al., 2022). However, these metrics are typically limited to small areas and lack broader applicability for cross-context comparisons. There remains a lack of a framework for understanding the principles and measuring the volumetric urban design.

The second defining feature of volumetric urban design in Hong Kong is the integration of the metro system. Hong Kong's reliance on the metro system is evident: nearly half the population lives within 500 metres of a station, and 70% of riders walk to and from the metro, contributing to an average daily ridership of 4.7 million (Sun et al., 2021). This approach promotes high-density, mixed land use, and enhanced connectivity within station catchment areas, consistent with transit-oriented development (TOD) principles. In addition, seamless integration of pedestrian networks with metro stations connects multi-level urban interfaces, supporting both urban connectivity and spatial integration (Villani et al., 2022). The expansion of underground and elevated spaces enables the vertical stacking of urban functions, creating environments that extend above and below ground (Zacharias & He, 2018; Zhang & Chiaradia, 2022). Metro stations are directly linked to commercial complexes and residential towers through comprehensive three-dimensional pedestrian networks, including footbridges, tunnels, elevators, and escalators. Elevated and underground walkways connect podiums, shopping malls, and towers, generating large, multi-layered volumes and enhancing walkability. Many building spaces, though privately owned yet publicly accessible, are integrated with metro stations, providing climate-controlled areas that serve both commuters and the general public (Shelton et al., 2013). The ongoing expansion of the metro and its integration with property developments have fostered pedestrian-oriented urban design, making three-dimensional connectivity a hallmark of the city's urban fabric. However, the complex interactions among multi-level connections and the spatial organisation of TOD in volumetric design warrant further investigation.

This paper measures three core attributes of volumetric urban design in Hong Kong: compression, connectedness, and functional mix. It addresses a critical gap in measuring multi-layered environments by proposing an operationalised method. We applied and validated these new measures in two areas with dense pedestrian and metro networks, which are featured as typical volumetric environments, to confirm their effectiveness. Furthermore, we examined how multi-level pedestrian networks expand connectivity, reinforce compression, and redistribute functions vertically and horizontally by connecting metro stations and surrounding buildings. The key results of this study were shown in the **Fig. 1- Fig. 5**. This research advances the spatial understanding of complex, multi-layered urban forms and provides novel tools for researchers and practitioners to analyse volumetric urban design in high-density cities.

2. Method

We developed operationalizable measures using fine-grained, open-access data to capture volumetric urban design, rather than applying these measures broadly for comparison across multiple areas. Central and TST were chosen as typical cases for their varied historical development, diverse building forms

(e.g., from colonial-era structures to modern high-rises on reclaimed land), representative volumetric design (e.g., extension of networks in three dimensions), and the implementation of TOD principles. The workflow of this study is shown in Fig. 2. We collected POI data from Gaode Map, which offers more comprehensive coverage of geographical entities in Hong Kong than official or other third-party sources. POI categories located outside buildings were excluded, resulting in 10 retained categories for analysis (e.g., catering, hotels, tourist attractions). To address positional inaccuracies, we manually corrected deviated POIs to ensure alignment with building footprints.

Data processing was involved in several steps. First, sidewalk boundaries were identified, and sidewalk widths were manually extracted in GIS based on street boundaries and building footprints. Since widths vary along each segment, we used the narrowest point to represent the minimum pedestrian movement capacity for each segment. For pedestrian network types not captured in the datasets, such as indoor, underground segments, and crossings, we referenced Hong Kong’s design criteria for width assessment. Second, floor information was extracted from POI address text using Python, allowing each POI to be assigned to a specific floor.

For compression, it was defined as the aggregated interaction opportunities between a building and its nearby buildings, mediated by multi-level pedestrian networks and accounting for distance decay. We applied a gravity-based model, commonly used to measure spatial interactions.

Fig. 1 Analytical framework

Fig. 2 Data processing

We defined connectedness as the indicator measuring the public interface that can be reached within walking distance from each building. The measure is a proxy for the walkable and permeable interface that pedestrians encounter. The calculation refers to the aggregation of walkable space of different street segments in catchment areas; a higher score indicates that a larger street space accommodates pedestrians.

We assessed the functional mix of each building across three categories—live, visit, and work—using a ternary graph (Dovey & Pafka, 2017), which graphically represents the composition of three variables in a two-dimensional triangle. Each point's position on the plot corresponds to its trilinear (barycentric) coordinates, enabling intuitive visualisation of functional composition. Functional mix was interpreted using the parallel line method, where lines parallel to each triangle edge indicate constant values for the corresponding function at each vertex.

Fig. 3 Visualisation of compression and connectedness in the study areas: (a) Compression in Central area; (b) Compression in TST area; (c) Connectedness in Central area; and (d) Connectedness in TST area.

Fig. 4 Visualisation of functional mix in the study areas: (a) Ternary graphs of the building overall and vertical functional mix in Central and TST; (b) Building overall functional mix in Central; (c) Building vertical functional mix in Central; (d) Building overall functional mix in TST; and (e) Building vertical functional mix in TST

Fig. 5 Contributions of elevated walkways to volumetric design outcomes: (a) Changes in compression if without elevated walkways; (b) Changes in connectedness if without elevated walkways; (c) Changes in functional mix at floor-level of the buildings connected by elevated walkways

3. Acknowledgements

This study is partly funded by the NSFC (No. 52078446). The funder had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

References

- Al-Kodmany, K. (2018). *The vertical city: a sustainable development model*. WIT press.
- Bruyns, G. J., Higgins, C. D., & Nel, D. H. (2021). Urban volumetrics: From vertical to volumetric urbanisation and its extensions to empirical morphological analysis. *Urban Studies*, 58(5), 922-940.
- Dovey, K., & Pafka, E. (2017). What is functional mix? An assemblage approach. *Planning Theory & Practice*, 18(2), 249-267.
- Dovey, K., & Pafka, E. (2020). What is walkability? The urban DMA. *Urban studies*, 57(1), 93-108.
- Harris, A. (2015). Vertical urbanisms: Opening up geographies of the three-dimensional city. *Progress in Human Geography*, 39(5), 601-620.
- Lehmann, S. (2016). Sustainable urbanism: towards a framework for quality and optimal density? *Future cities and environment*, 2, 1-13.
- Lin, Z., & Gámez, J. L. (2018). *Vertical urbanism: designing compact cities in China*. Routledge.
- McNeill, D. (2020). The volumetric city. *Progress in Human Geography*, 44(5), 815-831.
- Pafka, E. (2023). Modelling, mapping and measuring urban densities. In *The Routledge Handbook of Urban Design Research Methods* (pp. 460-469). Routledge.
- Shelton, B., Karakiewicz, J., & Kvan, T. (2013). *The making of Hong Kong: from vertical to volumetric*. Routledge.
- Sun, G., Webster, C., & Zhang, X. (2021). Connecting the city: a three-dimensional pedestrian network of Hong Kong. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 48(1), 60-75.
- Tan, Z., & QL Xue, C. (2014). Walking as a planned activity: Elevated pedestrian network and urban design regulation in Hong Kong. *Journal of urban Design*, 19(5), 722-744.
- Thill, J.-C., Dao, T. H. D., & Zhou, Y. (2011). Traveling in the three-dimensional city: applications in route planning, accessibility assessment, location analysis and beyond. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 19(3), 405-421.
- Villani, C., Talamini, G., & Xue, C. Q. (2022). Pedestrian access to transit in evolution: unfolding the spatialization of rapid-transit planning. *Journal of Urban Design*, 27(6), 669-691.
- Wandl, A., & Hausleitner, B. (2021). Investigating functional mix in Europe's dispersed urban areas. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 48(9), 2862-2879.
- Wang, W. (2020). Everyday practice in the high density, volumetric Hong Kong: Ambiguity, intensity and life between interfaces. *Cities*, 96, 102462.
- Zacharias, J. (2021). Pedestrian dynamics on narrow pavements in high-density Hong Kong. *Journal of Urban Management*, 10(4), 409-418.
- Zacharias, J., & He, J. (2018). Hong Kong's urban planning experiment in enhancing pedestrian movement from underground space to the surface. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 82, 1-8.
- Zhao, J., Sun, G., & Webster, C. (2021). Walkability scoring: Why and how does a three-dimensional pedestrian network matter? *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 48(8), 2418-2435.

Biographies

Dr. Dongsheng He is a Research Fellow at the University of Leeds, UK. His mainly focuses on how urban infrastructure (e.g., metro system) is provided and its impacts in Asian countries. His ongoing projects investigate the impacts of broader transport interventions (e.g., transit-oriented development and bike lane improvement) and transport policy (e.g., work from home adoption).

Dr Guibo Sun is a Lecturer in Urban Planning at the University of Manchester. His research examines how major urban infrastructure shapes cities and affects social and health outcomes, spanning the intersections of planning, land policy, transportation, urban design, and public health.